

53 Days of Preventive Medicine

International Congress

24-27. September 2019.
Niš, Serbia

BOOK OF ABSTRACTS

Public Health Institute Niš

Faculty of Medicine,
University of Niš

Serbian Medical Society, Niš

Niš, 2019.

Editor in Chief

Уредник

Prof. dr Zoran Milošević

Technical Editor

Технички уредник

dipl. ing. Stefan Bogdanović

Publisher

Издавач

Public Health Institute Niš - Институт за јавно здравље Ниш

Faculty of Medicine Niš, University of Niš - Медицински факултет у Нишу, Универзитет у Нишу

Serbian Medical Society, Niš - Српско лекарско друштво подружница Ниш

For publisher

За издавача

Prof. dr Miodrag Stojanović

Printed in

Штампарија и место штампања

Галаксија, Ниш, Србија

Number of copies

Тираж

300

Under the patronage of

Под покровитељством

Ministry of Education, Science and Technological Development of the Republic of Serbia

Министарства просвете, науке и технолошког развоја Републике Србије

Ministry of Health of the Republic of Serbia

Министарства здравља Републике Србије

All abstracts are published in the book of abstracts in the form in which they were submitted by the authors, who are responsible for their content.

Сви сажетци су публиковани у зборнику резимеа у облику у коме су достављени од стране аутора, који су одговорни за њихов садржај.

The content of this publication is available online at dpm.izjz-nis.org.rs

Садржај ове публикације је доступан на Интернет адреси dpm.izjz-nis.org.rs

The continuing education program number A-1-1174/19 was accredited by the decision of the Health Council of the Republic of Serbia No. 153-02-1413/2019-01 from 20. 05. 2019.

Програм континуиране едукације је под бројем А-1-1174/19 акредитован одлуком Здравственог савета Републике Србије број: 153-02-1413/2019-01 од 20. 05. 2019. године.

ISBN 978-86-900283-0-6

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CIP - Каталогизacija у публикацији - Народна библиотека Србије, Београд

614.4(048)(0.034.2)

616-084(048)(0.034.2)

INTERNATIONAL Congress Days of Preventive Medicine (53 ; 2019 ; Niš)

Book of Abstracts [Elektronski izvor] / 53rd Days of Preventive Medicine, International Congress, 24-27. September 2019. Niš ; [editor in chief, уредник Zoran Milošević]. - Niš : Public Health Institute : Faculty of Medicine : Serbian Medical Society, 2019 (Ниш : Галаксија).

-1 elektronski optički disk (CD-ROM) ; 12 cm

Sistemska zahtevi: Nisu navedeni.

-Nasl. sa naslovne strane

dokumenta.

-Tiraž 300.

-Bibliografija uz pojedine apstrakte.

ISBN 978-86-900283-0-6 (PHI)

a) Превентивна медицина - Апстракти

COBISS.SR-ID 280232716

8. MEDICAL DEVICES INTENDED FOR SELF-MONITORING OF BLOOD GLUCOSE AVAILABLE IN SERBIA

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Objectives: The aim of this research was to identify blood glucose monitoring devices (glucometers) registered in Serbia and assess their selected properties.

Methods: Online search of the National Medical Devices Database was performed using “aparatus za određivanje glukoze u krvi” as a search string (under “generic name”). Detailed information on specific glucometers was found on manufacturers’ websites.

Results: A total of 20 glucometers for personal use from 12 different manufacturers were registered in Serbia according to the National Medical Devices Database. Countries of origin were China (4 manufacturers), Germany (2), Switzerland (2), South Korea (2), Taiwan (1), Austria (1). Measuring ranges varied slightly between different glucometers, most commonly being from 0.6 or 1.1 mmol/l to 33.3 mmol/l. Accuracy of all glucometers was declared to be in accordance with the ISO 15197 standard. Storage capacity was between 250 and 1000 test results (usually 300 or 500) with possibilities to display 1 to 90 days averages (most commonly 7, 14 or 30 days). Prices of different models varied from 20 to 80 EUR.

Conclusions: Considering the differences between glucometers registered in Serbia, possibly confusing for patients, healthcare professionals should be educated to help diabetics find glucometers that best fit their specific needs.

Keywords: medical devices; database; glucometers; blood glucose; Serbia